

Maintenance Plan

“23 Things Revisited: Field Guides to Research data Management”

Deliverable project phase 4, d.d. 28/09/2020

Ensuring sustainable access to project results

The 23 Things project, funded by an RDA Adoption Grant, ran from June 2019 to September 2020. The project has been executed under the responsibility of the National Coordination Point RDM (LCRDM). The project team consisted of members of the LCRDM expert pool, who explicitly collaborated with stakeholders in the Netherlands and abroad, to develop the different audience versions of the 23 things. This maintenance plan is to make sure that the deliverables of the project stay up to date and remain useful for the Dutch RDM community as well as for other communities wishing to adopt the deliverables themselves.

The project’s deliverables are:

1. An intermediate general and several audience specific versions, published as .doc and .pdf on Zenodo
2. Tool in Wordpress
3. Project documents published on Zenodo

The project first worked at creating different versions of the 23 Things: an intermediate version, which served to adapt the 23 things to the current Dutch situation. This version was then used to create ‘audience specific’ versions. All versions are published in Zenodo, but only the intermediate version has been adapted to the original format of two pages A4. The content of the audience specific versions is used to fill the tool (deliverable 2) and it is likely that people will use the tool rather than the PDF versions. However, the published versions of the ‘23 thing’s should also be updated on a regular, but less frequent basis.

The tool was inspired by the Cornell University Data Storage finder and adopted by Utrecht University (UU). UU further developed and, on request of the National Coordination Point RDM, hosts the 23 things tool for general use. Information in the tool needs regular updating, such as repairing broken links or adding new essential resources. Also, in the future, new functionalities may become necessary, for instance for training purposes. It is the intention to make all materials (code, template, underlying database) available with the project documents (deliverable 3) for others to rebuild the tool for their own community.

The project documents are all published on Zenodo for other communities to use for their own adoption and implementation. In principle, these documents do not need to be maintained. However, new materials may be added in the future.

Roles in the maintenance of the project deliverables

Three roles are to be fulfilled in order to ensure appropriate maintenance and sustainable access to the deliverables of the project. The following model will be evaluated at the end of 2021.

I. Editorial board

The responsibility of the editorial board is to make sure that the content of the different versions and the tool is up-to-date. It:

- Replies to questions from users or from other adoption projects. These questions are addressed at LCRDM (info@lcrdm.nl)
- Updates information and links and documents changes to the tool
- Decides on changes to the content, suggested by the editors themselves or the general public
- Comes with suggestions for improvement on functional or technical level
- Can initiate new task groups or sprints to further develop tool and content
- Helps RDA promote similar adoption projects

The board is composed by five members, to start with members of the task group that created the tool. If one of the members leaves the board, a new member is recruited in principle via a public announcement to the LCRDM expert pool, striving towards a representation of different stakeholders. The board meets every two months.

Time investment:

- Members of the editorial board: 25 hours per year per member
- Editor and contact person at LCRDM: 40 hours per year

II. Functional maintenance

Functional maintenance lies with LCRDM and SURF.

The functional manager:

- Manages the authorisations for the tool
- Manages the content database underlying the tool
- Supports the editorial board in updating the content of the tool
- Can initiate new functionalities
- Signals possibilities to improve the interoperability of content and tool
- Collaborates with technical manager in case updates or migrations are needed
- Delivers management information (number of views etc.) to the editorial board

Time investment: 48 hours per year

III. Technical maintenance

LCRDM is the 'owner' of the tool, but the technical maintenance lies with the UU. A Service Level Agreement will be signed.

The technical manager:

- Makes sure that the tool remains accessible, whatever platform updates may occur
- Implement (minimal) changes to the tool to improve its usability on request of the editorial board and/or functional manager
- Promotes open source development by sharing code or template of the tool in a public repository (in order to make other adoption projects benefit from the work already done)
- Collaborates with the functional manager in case of updates or migrations to another platform

Time investment: 20 hours per year

Conclusion

Developments are going very fast in the field of research data management, which proves both the need for a tool like the one produced in the course of this project as well as the challenges that come with updating and maintaining the information it contains. Therefore, by the end of 2021, the approach described in this document will be evaluated and, if needed, be revised. This process will be initiated by the coordinator of the LCRDM.